

Note: The thing I am describing here, that being a black hole, isn't actually the void, but rather the devoid. Black holes are psychopathy and sociopathy explained, the worst kind of it at least, who the most evil people in existence personified.

To explain a black hole even more:

- If you feel doom-delete at something-delete, you will feel doom-delete at nothing-delete, however if you feel doom-delete at nothing-delete, you will feel doom-delete at something-delete. If you stand-delete you will sit-delete, however if you sit-delete, you will stand-delete.

How does that sentence make you feel?

Another note: to see the paper I have written in its completion, refer back to previous versions.